

Nuxalk

also known as “Bellacoola”

Data source: eHRAF

Secondary source

Entered by Emily Pitek, Human Relations Area Files

** Data Source entry, prepared based on data sourced from an external project.*

** Secondary Source entry, prepared from a literature review by a Ph.D. RA*

Entry tags: Religion, Native American (North American) Religions

The Nuxalk are a Canadian First Nations society who live in the Bella Coola valley of British Columbia. These people trace their ancestry back to the original settlers of the area, who were sent by the supreme god Äłquntäm. Because the Nuxalk religious beliefs are bound up in almost all spheres of life, this entry considers the religious group to be coterminous with the society. It is important to note that the Nuxalk beliefs were influenced by Christianity beginning with contact in the 18th century. Key features of the Nuxalk beliefs include a variety of supernatural beings, religious specialists (shamans) possessing supernatural powers, as well as rituals (most commonly dances) led by secret ceremonial societies called kisuit and siswak. This entry focuses on the Nuxalk ca. 1880, with emphasis placed on the central village of the lower Bella Coola river.

Date Range: 1860 CE - 1890 CE

Region: Bella Coola Valley Area

Region tags: North America, Canada

Bella Coola Valley area of British Columbia's central coast, specifically the central village of the lower Bella Coola river, ca. 1880

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources

Print sources for understanding this subject:

– Source 1: Divale, W. 2004. Codebook of Variables for the Standard Cross-Cultural Sample. *World Cultures: The Journal of Cross-Cultural and Comparative Research*.

Online sources for understanding this subject:

– Source 1 URL: <http://ehrafworldcultures.yale.edu/document?id=ne06-001>

– Source 1 Description: McIlwraith, T. F. (Thomas F. (1948). *Bella Coola Indians: Volume One*. Toronto: University of Toronto Press

– Source 2 URL: <http://ehrafworldcultures.yale.edu/document?id=ne06-002>

– Source 2 Description: McIlwraith, T. F. (Thomas F. (1948). *Bella Coola Indians: Volume Two*. Toronto: University of Toronto Press

– Source 3 URL: <http://ehrafworldcultures.yale.edu/document?id=ne06-006>

– Source 3 Description: Boas, Franz. 1892. "Third Report On The Indians Of British Columbia." Report Of The Sixty-First Meeting Of The British Association For The Advancement Of Science Held At Cardiff In August 1891. London: John Murray

Notes: Mcllwraith, 1948 Volume One will be referred to as Mcllwraith, 1948a; Mcllwraith, 1948 Volume Two will be referred to as Mcllwraith, 1948b;

– Source 1 URL: <http://ehrafworldcultures.yale.edu/document?id=ne06-000>

– Source 1 Description: Solomonian, A. A. (2011). Culture Summary: Nuxalk. New Haven, Conn.: Human Relations Area Files.

General Variables

Membership/Group Interactions

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

– Yes

Notes: "Documented Nuxalk interactions with non-native peoples extend as far back as 1793 when both Captain George Vancouver and Alexander Mackenzie encountered groups of Nuxalk during their separate travels into the Bella Coola region. By the late nineteenth century, Nuxalk contact with non-native outsiders was firmly entrenched in social, political and economic relations with the institutions of the nascent Canadian state. Increasing Euro-Canadian settlement in the Bella Coola Valley began with a party of Norwegian settlers moving into the area from Minnesota in 1894 and establishing the town of Hagensbourg. This was the first major non-native settlement in the Valley" (Solomonian, 2011).

↳ Is the cultural contact accommodating/pluralistic:

– Yes

Notes: "Heavily influenced by Christianity over the last century and a half, Nuxalk beliefs in recent years represent a unique integration of what might be deemed a more 'traditional' cosmology within the structure of a more contemporary Christian spiritual philosophy" (Solomonian, 2011).

↳ Is there violent conflict (within sample region):

– Yes

Notes: SCCS Variable 1648 (Overall frequency of warfare, resolved rating) indicates that internal warfare seems to occur between once every 3-10 years, and at least once every 2 years (Ember and Ember, 1992; Retrieved from Divale, 2004).

↳ Is there violent conflict (with groups outside the sample region):

– Yes

Notes: SCCS Variable 1648 (Overall frequency of warfare, resolved rating) indicates that external warfare seems to occur between once every 3-10 years, and at least once every 2 years (Ember and Ember, 1992; Retrieved from Divale, 2004).

Does the religious group have a general process/system for assigning religious affiliation:

– No

Notes: Because the religion is coterminous with the society, there is no concept of assigning religious affiliation other than being born into a family lineage.

Does the religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members:

– No

Notes: Because the religion is coterminous with the society, there is not a concept of recruiting new members.

Does the religion have official political support

Answer 'yes' also in cases where the religious and political spheres are not distinguished from one another, but the religious group's activities are tied up with, and supported by, the functioning of the society at large.

– No

Notes: SCCS Variable 1740 (Levels of political hierarchy) indicates that no political office is present among the Nuxalk (Lang, 1998; Retrieved from Divale, 2004). Because no formal political office is present, it cannot be said that the religion has official political support. However, the religious sphere is not distinguished from other aspects of life, and consequently the religious group is coterminous with the society at large.

Is there a conception of apostasy in the religious group:

– No

Size and Structure

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical):

– Estimated population, numeric: 400

Notes: See McIlwraith, 1948a:v,5 and Solomonian, 2011.

Are there recognized leaders in the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: "More important to the Bella Coola than any other manifestation of the supernatural is that power which makes an individual either an älukwala or an äskankots. The former is a person who, owing to ability granted him by a supernatural being, is able to perform miraculous feats, especially in curing the sick; the latter is one with similar powers obtained from a ghost. It is impossible to translate either of these terms accurately; the designation 'shaman' is accordingly used in this monograph to describe both types of supernaturally endowed individuals" (McIlwraith, 1948a:539).

Are leaders believed to possess supernatural powers or qualities:

– Yes

Powers are culturally transmitted from a supernatural being:

– Yes

Notes: "...a certain type of shaman is believed to receive power direct from him [Ätquntäm, the high god]" (McIlwraith, 1948a:38).

Scripture

Does the religious group have scriptures:

Scripture is a generic term used to designate revered texts that are considered particularly authoritative and sacred relative to other texts. Strictly speaking, it refers to written texts, but there are also "oral scriptures" (e.g. the Vedas of India).

– No

Notes: While mythology and oral traditions play a major role in the supernatural beliefs of the Nuxalk, there is no ethnographic evidence of scriptures.

Architecture, Geography

Is monumental religious architecture present:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of monumental religious architecture.

Are there different types of religious monumental architecture:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of monumental religious architecture.

Are there specific sites dedicated to sacred practice or considered sacred:

– Yes

Notes: Many environmental features are related to the supernatural through myths. McIlwraith, 1948a describes many of these places and stories. See pages 600-605 for examples.

Are sacred site oriented to environmental features:

"Environmental features" refers to features in the landscape, mountains, rivers, cardinal directions etc...

– Yes

Beliefs

Burial and Afterlife

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer “no” only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body. Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– Yes

Notes: "The most important part of the human body is the xixmänoäs, spirit. This is small, but of great power, since it belongs to the world of the supernatural; in fact, the spirit of a man is not mortal, but siut. Everyone, man or woman, rich or poor, chief or slave, has one; without it, life would be impossible" (McIlwraith, 1948a:94).

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as having qualitatively different powers or properties than other body parts:

– Yes

Notes: See McIlwraith, 1948a:94-97 for a detailed description of spirit properties.

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as non-material, ontologically distinct from body:

– Yes

Notes: "When a child is born, his parents supply him with food and care, and Äłquntäm provides the even more necessary invisible elements, including the spirit. It resides in the back of the neck and resembles a thin bone shaped like a maple-leaf" (McIlwraith, 1948a:94).

Belief in afterlife:

– Yes

Notes: "When a Bella Coola dies, his spirit travels back on the path of his ancestors from generation to generation until it reaches the spot where the first one came to earth; there it assumes the bird or animal cloak used on that occasion and floats aloft to Nusmät`a to live forever" (McIlwraith, 1948a:36).

↳ Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: See questions below for more detail.

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined “above” space:

– Yes

Notes: (McIlwraith, 1948a:36)

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined “below” space:

– Yes

Notes: "After four days the life [separate from the spirit] descends to the land below where it lives forever as a ghost" (McIlwraith, 1948a:99).

Reincarnation in this world:

– Yes

Notes: "It is thought, indefinitely, that after a long period of time the ghosts die, and some of them may then return to this world as infants. A child born with dimples in its ears, which are regarded as indications of previous borings for rings, is welcomed as the reincarnation of some unknown ancestor" (McIlwraith, 1948a:497).

↳ In a human form:

– Yes

Notes: (McIlwraith, 1948a:497)

↳ In animal/plant form:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for a belief in reincarnation in animal/plant form.

↳ In form of an inanimate object(s):

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for a belief in reincarnation in the form of an inanimate object.

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

– Yes

Notes: See questions below for more detailed information concerning the treatment of corpses among the Nuxalk.

↳ Cremation:

– Yes

Notes: "According to several of the older men, cremation was practised by the Bella Coola for some time after the first settlement of the earth. A fire was built outside the house and the body [Page 451] thrown on it. One rather philosophic old man suggested that in this way the soul could easily return to Nusmät`a. It is possible that this means of disposal was carried out in former times, but no informant had actually seen it practised" (McIlwraith, 1948a:450).

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1600 CE - 1700 CE

↳ Mummification:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of mummification.

↳ Interment:

– Yes

Notes: "At present, interment is the customary method for disposing of the bodies of all except twins, whose bodies are placed in trees" (McIlwraith, 1948a:450).

↳ Corpse is flexed (legs are bent or body is crouched):

– Yes

Notes: "The body is dressed in good clothing and bound into a squatting position, head between knees, hands clasped around shins, and the haunches just above the level of the soles of the feet. In this posture it is thrust into the coffin. Particularly if the corpse has been brought from some distance and rigor mortis has set in, it may be necessary to break the back-bone and even to crush the skull before the box can be closed. A stone is placed on the back of the neck, within the coffin, to prevent the ghost from returning to haunt the survivors. A little choice food is placed beside the body of a dearly loved child for nourishment during the journey to the next world" (McIlwraith, 1948a:437).

↳ Corpse is extended (lying flat on front or back):

– No

Notes: (McIlwraith, 1948a:437)

↳ Corpse is upright (where body is interred in standing position)::

– No

Notes: (McIlwraith, 1948a:437)

↳ Corpse is interred some other way:

– No

Notes: (McIlwraith, 1948a:437)

↳ Cannibalism:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of cannibalism.

↳ Exposure to elements (e.g. air drying):

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence indicating that corpses were exposed to the elements.

↳ Feeding to animals:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of feeding corpses to animals.

↳ Secondary burial:

– No

Notes: SCCS Variable 1850 (Secondary Bone/Body Treatment: Original Scale) indicates that "secondary contact with the body or bones of the deceased does not occur" (Schroeder, 2001; Retrieved from Divale, 2004).

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of co-sacrifices in tomb/burial.

Are grave goods present:

– Yes

Notes: "On arrival [at the cemetery], the pall-bearers set down their burden close to the spot where the guide has placed her flaming bark on the ground. The personal possessions of the deceased are likewise deposited near the fire, which is kept alight by female relatives throwing on it small quantities of the dead person's clothing and utensils" (Mcllwraith, 1948a:444).

↳ Personal effects:

– Yes

Notes: "On arrival [at the cemetery], the pall-bearers set down their burden close to the spot where the guide has placed her flaming bark on the ground. The personal possessions of the deceased are likewise deposited near the fire, which is kept alight by female relatives throwing on it small quantities of the dead person's clothing and utensils" (Mcllwraith, 1948a:444).

↳ Valuable items:

– No

Notes: Ethnographic evidence for grave goods only includes personal effects.

↳ Other grave goods:

– Yes

Notes: "There [beside the grave], too, must be laid dried salmon which a man has smoked for winter use, as well as pulverized berries and other foods made ready by a woman; to eat food prepared by a dead person seems indescribably indecent" (Mcllwraith, 1948a:454).

Are formal burials present:

– Yes

Notes: See Mcllwraith 1948a:443-452 for a detailed description of burial practices.

↳ As cenotaphs:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of cenotaphs.

↳ In cemetery:

– Yes

Notes: "There is a cemetery near every village, usually fifty to a hundred yards behind the row of houses in a place from which the heavy timber has been cleared" (McIlwraith, 1948a:444).

↳ Family tomb-crypt:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of a family tomb-crypt

↳ Domestic (individuals interred beneath house, or in areas used for normal domestic activities):

– Yes

Notes: "At present, interment is the customary method for disposing of the bodies of all except twins, whose bodies are placed in trees. Formerly, other means were sometimes employed, as they still are occasionally. Instead of inhumation, a coffin was frequently placed on a scaffold close behind the deceased's house. Whenever another relative died, planks were laid across, above the first box, and the new one deposited on these, so that in time the scaffold grew to resemble a house-like structure with many compartments. In the last century a certain shaman, Āskānkots by name, is said to have pointed out that corpses were frequently carried off by wolves, sniniq, and other animals. For this reason he persuaded the people to inter their dead" (McIlwraith, 1948a:450).

↳ Other formal burial type:

– Yes [specify]: Above ground

Notes: "Even at the present time, the corpse of a dearly loved child is occasionally placed above, instead of under the ground. If the parents desire to do this, they erect in the cemetery a carved figure of one of their crests and deposit the coffin on top of it. This is, of course, a graphic representation of the deceased's origin myth and symbolizes the way in which the dead person has become associated with it" (McIlwraith, 1948a:450).

Supernatural Beings

Are supernatural beings present:

– Yes

Notes: See questions below for more details on the nature of Nuxalk supernatural beings.

↳ A supreme high god is present:

– Yes

Notes: "The Bella Coola agree that the most important of their supernatural beings is Ālquntām, the supreme deity, maker of men and animals. He is most commonly known by

this name but he has other appellations with reference to his various functions. The word Äłquntäm is said to be derived from ıxquntäm, "foreman," or "chief." He is chief of the supernatural beings" (McIlwraith, 1948a:32).

↳ The supreme high god is anthropomorphic:

– Yes

Notes: "In form he resembles a man..." (McIlwraith, 1948a:33).

↳ The supreme high god is a sky deity:

– Yes

Notes: "Though Äłquntäm often sojourns in the sun, his home is in the flat land above the sky, a huge house which figures prominently both in Bella Coola mythology and present-day thought. The name of the house is Nusmät`a. It resembles those constructed on this earth, but is boundless in size" (McIlwraith, 1948a:34).

↳ The supreme high god is fused with the monarch (king=high god):

– No

Notes: No monarch is present among the Nuxalk.

↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:

– No

Notes: No monarch is present among the Nuxalk.

↳ The supreme high god is unquestionably good:

– I don't know

↳ The supreme high god has knowledge of this world:

– I don't know

↳ The supreme high god has deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– I don't know

↳ The supreme high god has indirect causal efficacy in the world:

"Indirect causal efficacy" refers to not being seen as consciously, directly and actively intervening in the human world, but their overall well being or general attitude has effects on, e.g., quality of harvest, success in war, health, etc.

– I don't know

↳ Is it permissible to worship supernatural beings other than the high god:

– Yes

Notes: "Other supernatural beings may work weal or woe to a Bella Coola, but he feels it is done with the sanction of Äłquntäm" (McIlwraith, 1948a:38). "Although Äłquntäm, under the name of Minakais, is the one to whom prayers are most often addressed, petitions are sometimes made to other beings" (McIlwraith, 1948a:106).

↳ Previously human spirits are present:

– Yes

Notes: "Quite another category of Bella Coola supernatural beings consists of ghosts. These beings, once human, have passed by death into the ranks of the supernatural" (McIlwraith, 1948a:55).

↳ Human spirits can be seen:

– Yes

Notes: "Mortals sometimes see ghosts, but the apparition seals their lips so that they cannot recount their experiences. Death invariably follows" (McIlwraith, 1948a:55).

↳ Human spirits can be physically felt:

– I don't know

Notes: Insufficient ethnographic information.

↳ Previously human spirits have knowledge of this world:

– Yes

Notes: "They [spirits of the deceased] can see what is taking place on earth and sometimes return in bird or animal form to visit and comfort their grieving relatives" (McIlwraith, 1948a:96).

↳ Human spirits have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– No

Notes: "The spirit and the life of a dead person have gone too far away to affect the living..." (McIlwraith, 1948a:496).

↳ Human spirits have indirect causal efficacy in the world:

"Indirect causal efficacy" refers to not being seen as consciously, directly and actively intervening in the human world, but their overall well being or general attitude has effects on, e.g., quality of harvest, success in war, health, etc.

– I don't know

↳ Human spirits possess hunger:

– Yes

Notes: "Food is scarce in that land and ghosts are often driven up to earth to search for it. Even a small morsel is enough to satisfy their hunger, so that mortals throw fragments on the fire for the benefit of their dead relatives" (McIlwraith, 1948a:55).

↳ Human spirits communicate with the living:

– Yes

Notes: "They can visit the land of the living at will, and make their presence known by whistling, which is their language" (McIlwraith, 1948a:55).

↳ Only through specialists:

– Yes

Notes: "They [ghosts] are always dreaded, and anyone who hears their whistling or their tongueless chatter cowers in his house, and hopes they will pass by. Shamans can understand their speech and to them the dead explain their mission" (McIlwraith, 1948a:499).

↳ Non-human supernatural beings are present:

– Yes

Notes: "The attitude of mingled hope and fear with which the Bella Coola regard their supernatural anthropomorphic beings is typical of their thoughts and actions concerning zoomorphic creatures as well. In the supernatural world the dividing line between human and animal beings is not clearly defined; fabulous monsters have the mentality of supermen, and can be appeased, besought, or cajoled precisely as are anthropomorphic beings. Like those of human form, supernatural animals can bestow good or evil on human beings with whom they come in contact" (McIlwraith, 1948a:59).

↳ These supernatural beings can be seen:

– Yes

Notes: "Of slightly greater importance is the hermaphrodite, S□ints. He resides in the land above, and spends most of his time outside the walls of Nusmät`a, acting as guardian to a number of young girls, the children of various supernatural beings. On many occasions he has descended to this world and has been seen by mortals, who recognize him by his peculiar nasal voice, intermediate between that of a man and a woman" (McIlwraith, 1948a:45).

↳ These supernatural beings can be physically felt:

– I don't know

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world:

– I don't know

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

Notes: "The religious concepts of the Bella Coola are not limited to explanations of strange apparitions, nor to knowledge of a wide range of supernatural beings, anthropomorphic or zoomorphic. Many in whom they believe are invisible and intangible, though none the less potent. Almost every incident of life is attributed to the help or hindrance of a supernatural agency" (McIlwraith, 1948a:57).

↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world:

"Indirect causal efficacy" refers to not being seen as consciously, directly and actively intervening in the human world, but their overall well being or general attitude has effects on, e.g., quality of harvest, success in war, health, etc.

– I don't know

↳ These supernatural beings possess/exhibit some other feature:

– Yes [specify]: Cause nightmares

Notes: "A supernatural being from whom many Bella Coola have had unpleasant visitations is S^himsila, the cause of nightmares" (McIlwraith, 1948a:46).

↳ Does the religious group possess a variety of supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Organized hierarchically:

– No

Notes: "Compared with Äquntäm, other supernatural beings are insignificant. The Bella Coola do not regard them as a hierarchy with definitely graded rank and power; accordingly, the order in which they are described is immaterial" (McIlwraith, 1948a:39).

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present:

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans' behaviour and/or thought particularly as it relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

– No

Notes: Based upon the sum of available ethnographic evidence, it does not appear that supernatural beings are actively involved in human's behavior as it relates to norms.

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of messianic beliefs.

Norms and Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: The Nuxalk prescribe many social norms, such as those surrounding death (McIlwraith, 1948a:457), potlatch rites (ibid, pg.192), and social control (ibid, pg. 147).

Practices

Membership Costs and Practices

Does membership in this religious group require celibacy (full sexual abstinence):

– No

Notes: See McIlwraith, 1948a:110

Does membership in this religious group require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence):

– No

Notes: While not required, ceremonial chastity is linked to the supernatural. "In addition to prayer and sacrifice, the Bella Coola have yet another means of obtaining the goodwill of supernatural beings, and at the same time of strengthening their own supernatural attributes so that good fortune is likely to occur. This is by the practice of sxetsta, ceremonial chastity, of which the basis is that a man must not hold intercourse except after certain periods of continence" (McIlwraith, 1948a:110).

Does membership in this religious group require castration:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of required castration.

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of adults:

"Adults" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition of a human who is 18-years-old or older and who is legally responsible for his/her actions, then please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence of human sacrifice.

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of children:

"Children" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition, please specify that different in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence of human sacrifice.

Does membership in this religious group require self-sacrifice (suicide):

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence of human sacrifice.

Does membership in this religious group require participation in large-scale rituals:

i.e. involving two or more households; includes large-scale “ceremonies” and “festivals.”

– I don't know

Notes: Rituals and ceremonies are generally divided between the kisuit and sisawk ceremonial societies. The kisuit is a secret, semi-religious group most importantly associated with the Winter Ceremonials. These performances are related to the supernatural world and supernatural beings. Membership in the sisawk ceremonial society is passed down through family lineages. The sisawk performances involve elaborate mask dances linked to ancestral families. (See McIlwraith, 1948b:1-5). It is unclear whether membership in these societies is required, but the societies play a significant role in the function of ritual activity among the Nuxalk.

Society and Institutions

Levels of Social Complexity

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

This question refers to the wider society in which the religious group is located.

– A band

Notes: "...chieftainship among the Bella Coola does not depend on hereditary rank, still less on an elective principle, but on the individual's prestige as displayed, especially in his ability to acquire for himself a firm seat by the giving of presents. As he continues to do so his influence becomes ever greater. Consequently, it is impossible to state clearly what are the powers of a chief; such depend upon his prestige and influence. For a Bella Coola chief has no executive or judicial authority; what deference is shown to him depends on his success as a man, a factor which is constantly rising or falling" (McIlwraith, 1948a:173). Additionally, the Nuxalk have no political authority beyond the local community, which is indicative of autonomous bands and villages (Ethnographic Atlas column 33, Murdock, 1967; retrieved from Divale, 2004).

Education

Does the religious group provide formal education to its adherents:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence of either formal religious or secular education. (See McIlwraith, 1948a:368).

Is formal education available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group:

– I don't know

Notes: Insufficient ethnographic information.

Bureaucracy

Do the group's adherents interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group:

– No

Notes: The Nuxalk have no political authority beyond the local community, which is indicative of autonomous bands and villages (Ethnographic Atlas column 33, Murdock, 1967; retrieved from Divale, 2004). Also see McIlwraith, 1948a:173

Public Works

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

– No

Notes: According to SCCS variable 20, food storage, food is stored in individual households (Murdock and Morrow, 1970; Retrieved from Divale, 2004).

Does the religious group in question provide water management (irrigation, flood control):

– No

Notes: The Nuxalk do not have irrigation. Source of information from Ethnographic Atlas (Murdock, 1962-1971), retrieved from Divale, 2004; Variables 203-207, 232.

Does the religious group in question provide transportation infrastructure:

– No

Notes: It can be assumed that transportation infrastructure is not present, as routes of land transport are "unimproved trails", according to Murdock and Morrow (1970; Retrieved from Divale, 2004; SCCS Variable 14).

Taxation

Does the religious group in question levy taxes or tithes:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of taxation among the Nuxalk.

Are taxes levied on the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of taxation (of any kind) among the Nuxalk.

Enforcement

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

– No

Notes: "Police functions are not specialized or institutionalized at any level of political integration, the maintenance of law and order being left exclusively to informal mechanisms of social control, private retaliation, or to sorcery" (Tuden and Marshall, column 10; note, equivalent to SCCS Variable 90 Police).

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized judges:

– No

Notes: SCCS Variable 89, Judiciary, indicates that a judiciary is absent among the Nuxalk (Tuden and Marshall, 1972; Retrieved from Divale, 2004). Ethnographic evidence indicates that informal in-group justice is present. Violations of kusiut (ceremonial society) laws and ceremonies are informally dealt with and are sometimes brought to the attention of a chief (see McIlwraith, 1948a:192; Boas, 1892:417). Social control and justice are typically the family's responsibility (McIlwraith, 1948a:147).

Does the religious group in question enforce institutionalized punishment:

– No

Notes: Ethnographic evidence indicates that informal in-group justice (and punishment) is present. A standardized, institutional form of punishment is not present among the Nuxalk. Violations of kusiut (ceremonial society) laws and ceremonies are informally dealt with and are sometimes brought to the attention of a chief (see McIlwraith, 1948a:192; Boas, 1892:417). Social control and justice are typically the family's responsibility (McIlwraith, 1948a:147).

Does the religious group in question have a formal legal code:

– No

Notes: Because there is no formal or institutional means of social control, it can be inferred that a formal legal code is not present. (See previous questions on enforcement).

Food Production

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

– Yes

Notes: The Nuxalk rely mainly on fishing for subsistence. Hunting and gathering provide secondary sources of subsistence. Source of information from Ethnographic Atlas (Murdock, 1962-1971), retrieved from Divale, 2004; Variables 203-207, 232.

Please characterize the forms/level of food production [choose all that apply]:

– Gathering

– Hunting (including marine animals)

– Fishing

Notes: The Nuxalk rely mainly on fishing for subsistence. Hunting and gathering provide

secondary sources of subsistence. Source of information from Ethnographic Atlas (Murdock, 1962-1971), retrieved from Divale, 2004; Variables 203-207, 232.